

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B317
Date: 15 August 2007
Take Off: 11:51:55Z
Landing: 16:22:55Z
Flight Time: 4h31m00s

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Baden Baden

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM 1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stephen Mobbs	NCAS
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist 2	Justin Peter	University of Leeds
9	Observer	Victoria Smith	University of Leeds
10	COPS	Volker Wulfmeyer	COPS
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Flight Track:

B317 Track 15-AUG-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B317
 Date: 15 August 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Baden Baden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
094506		Start-Up	0.52 kft	161	48'46.90N ,8'05.35E
115155		T/O	1.0 kft	212	Baden Baden
115912		Video	6.1 kft	014	Start FFC & UFC
120142	121542	Run 1.1	5.7 kft	188	5.5k' QNH 1008, C-B
120752		Event	5.7 kft	199	Abeam M
121229		Heimann	5.7 kft	196	Cal
121848	123123	Run 1.2	5.7 - 5.6 kft	013	B-C, 5.5k'
122718		Event	5.6 kft	013	Abeam Hornisgrinde
123447	125039	Run 2.1	6.5 kft	216	C-B
124032		Event	6.5 kft	193	Deviate twds Cu
124317		Event	6.5 kft	194	Below Cu
125358	130644	Run 2.2	6.5 kft	007	B-C
130034		Event	6.5 kft	012	Below Cu
130143		Event	6.5 kft	042	Below Cu
130206		Event	6.5 kft	040	Below Cu
131017	132557	Run 3.1	7.5 kft	204	At cloud level, C-B
132337		Event	7.5 kft	201	Thru cloud base
132912	134154	Run 3.2	7.5 kft	012	B-C
133200		Video	7.5 kft	024	Change Tapes
134519	140100	Run 4.1	8.5 kft	201	C-B
135648		Event	8.5 kft	198	Thru cloud
140407	141643	Run 4.2	8.5 kft	003	B-C
140754		Event	8.5 kft	021	Thru cloud
141125		Event	8.5 kft	357	Thru cloud
141125	144200	Run 5	8.5 kft		Into box, in cloud
141850		Event	9.4 kft	109	Thru cloud
144200	145305	Profile 1	10.0 - 20.0 kft	210	Into box, Interrupt @FL100
145519	150056	Profile 1	20.0 - 25.0 kft	039	
150146		Video	25.0 kft	086	Change Tapes
150323	150811	Profile 2	25.0 - 20.1 kft	218	
151035	151524	Run 6	20.1 - 20.0 kft	039	
152302	152824	Run 7	15.0 kft	027	1k' below tops
153047	153458	Run 8	14.0 kft	163	Through cloud
153817	154307	Run 9	15.0 kft	071	
154519	154928	Run 10	15.5 kft	197	
155106	155432	Run 11	16.0 kft	335	
155732	160228	Run 12	16.5 kft	278	
161052	161639	Run 13	5.2 kft	280	5.5k' Q1005, Over Supersites
161213		Event	5.2 kft	285	Ovhd M
161438		Event	5.2 kft	289	Ovhd H
161626		Event	5.2 kft	287	Ovhd R
162255		Land	0.62 kft	122	Baden Baden
162859		Shutdown	0.63 kft	160	48'46.91N, 8'05.35E

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B317 Track 15-AUG-07

PROJECT BRIEF: COPS - Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study.

Scientific Aims: The goals of UK-COPS are to determine the mechanisms for transport of aerosols into the convective clouds that form over the Black Forest mountains, to determine the properties of the aerosols and to understand the formation and growth of ice and precipitation in these clouds. We wish to examine:

- the structure of the thermally driven, turbulent boundary-layer flows below cloud base
- the properties of the representative aerosol particles in the clear air that are transported into the convective clouds
- the concentration and size of cloud droplets just above cloud base
- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

There will be one flight per day to observe the airflow and aerosol properties entering the convective clouds and most importantly, the properties of the clouds themselves. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C.

Weather conditions:

Developing showers over the Black Forest mountains, Germany, within Box A and probably B.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning.

Key instruments and their operation:

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe. When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP, CIP, SID-1 and SID-2. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator whilst in clear air runs.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode; above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode

Sortie Brief: COPS – Convective and Orographically-induced Precipitation Study
Flight Number: B316
Date: 15 August 2007
Mission Scientists:
TO Time: local

Sortie Aims: To measure properties of aerosols and airflow in the clear air and the development of convective clouds.

Sortie Location: Clear air above Murg Valley and in convective clouds over Black Forest mountains. Leg over supersites.

Sortie Summary:

1. Observe the boundary layer structure over one of the principal valleys penetrating the Black Forest mountain region.
2. Characterise properties of aerosols in clear air at low levels over the Black Forest, and the airflow over the Black Forest.
3. Penetrate cumulus clouds preferably near the top of the cloud in the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be with *wings level*. Two principal options are:
 - A stationary cloud or system of clouds;
 - B several cumulus clouds either in area (low wind) or passing through the area;
4. Characterise properties of aerosols in detrainment layers around cloud.
5. Overfly supersites M, H and R.

Sortie Detail:

1. Out-of-Cloud: All changes in altitude at standard rates (1000 ft/min).

Proceed to point C. Straight and level legs over the Murg Valley along track C-B and returning along track B-C (as flight B312, 26 July). Repeat at 5.0, 6.0 and 7.5 kft above mean sea level.

2. Cloud work:

Note an important feature is to ascend with tops. This requires a non-standard ascent as fast as possible.

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with the clouds near their top. All penetrations at constant altitude.

A.1 Proceed to about 0°C or top of cloud.

A.2 Adjust altitude to about 1000 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude if possible. It is important to penetrate the growing turret in the updraught region. A few seconds after clearing cloud, turn and ascend for return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible using procedure turn.

A.3 Repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) at the end of each penetration out of cloud, until FL200 or FL240, or cloud becomes too developed.

A.4 Repeat A.1 - A.4 for a new developing cumulus, go to **Option B**, or exit box.

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample clouds at constant altitude.

B.1 Proceed to 0°C

B.2 Commence 10 min runs (turning where appropriate) in along shear direction. Adjust track to randomly sample the updraught regions of growing turrets.

B.3 Ascend to -5°C (i.e. approximately 3500 ft) and repeat above for 10 min.

B.4 Repeat for -10°C , -15°C and -20°C if possible.

3. Detrainment layers

Proceed to level where cloud is being detrained from cloud and either make penetrations or circle around the cloud.

4. Leg over supersites Murg Valley (M), Hornisgrinde (H) and Achern (R) at about 5500 ft if in clear air. (15 min). Please make SATCOM phone call to Ops Centre 15 mins before overpass of Supersites: 07229 66 2550, or 2551.

EDSB -> EDDS - Overview

NavData Cycle 2007-7 Expires: Thursday, 02 August 2007.
Scale: 1:426851 (1 inch = 5.85 naut mi). Printed on 18 Jul 2007

JEPPESEN
FliteStar 9.2.0.2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B317

Date: 15/08/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:01:42																Start run 1.1 @ FL055	
12:02:00	320	0.08	1	5	1												
12:04:00	360	0.08		5	1												
12:06:00	600	0.08		2	1												
12:08:00	480	0.08		2	1												
12:10:00	230	0.08		2													
12:12:00	300	0.08		2													
12:14:00	230	0.08		2													
12:15:42																End of Run 1.1	
12:18:48																Start Run 1.1 @ FL057	
12:19:00	110	0.08	2	1	1												
12:21:00	260	0.08		2	1												
12:23:00	270	0.08		2	1												
12:25:00	380	0.08		2	1												
12:27:00	550	0.08		3													
12:29:00	400	0.08		2	1												
12:31:23																End of Run 1.2	
12:34:48																Start Run 2.1 @ FL065	
12:35:00	240	0.08	3	3													
12:37:00	55	0.08		2													
12:39:00	125	0.08		2													
12:41:00	75	0.08		2													
12:43:00	110	0.08		2													
12:45:00	200	0.08		2													
12:47:00	150	0.08		2													
12:49:00	190	0.08		2													
12:50:39																End of Run 2.1	
12:53:58																Start Run 2.2 @ FL065	
12:54:00	205	0.08		2													
12:56:00	250	0.08		2													
12:58:00	210	0.08	4	2													
13:00:00	160	0.08		2													
13:02:00	340	0.08		2													
13:04:00	180	0.07		2	1												
13:06:00	430	0.08		2	1												
13:06:44																End of Run 2.2	
13:10:16																Start Run 3.1 @ FL075	
13:11:00	150	0.08		2	1												
13:13:00	110	0.08		2	1												
13:15:00	25	0.08		2	1												
13:17:00	150	0.08		2	1												
13:19:00	270	0.08		2	1												
13:21:00	110	0.08		2													
13:23:00	150	0.08	5	2	1												
13:25:00	180	0.08		2	1												
13:25:57																End of Run 3.1	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B317

Date: 15/08/07 **Operator:** MAP **DRS Time:** 09:35:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 2 of 4**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
13:29:12																Start Run 3.2 @ FL075	
13:30:00	110	0.08	5	2	1												
13:32:00	340	0.08		2	1												
13:34:00	120	0.08		2													
13:36:00	150	0.08		2													
13:38:00	130	0.08		2													
13:40:00	180	0.08		2													
13:41:54																End of Run 3.2	
13:45:21																Start Run 4.1 @ FL085	
13:46:00	190	0.09		3	1												
13:48:00	170	0.08		3	1												
13:50:00	120	0.08		3	1												
13:52:00	130	0.08	6	2	1												
13:54:00	200	0.08		2	1												
13:56:00	95	0.08		2													
13:58:00	400	0.08	10	2	1												
14:00:00	250	0.08	43	2	1												
14:01:01																End of Run 4.1	
14:04:07																Start Run 4.2 @ FL085	
14:05:00	300	0.08		2	1												
14:07:00	220	0.08	44	2	1												
14:09:00	200	0.08	146	3	1												
14:11:00	150	0.08		2	1												
14:13:00	190	0.08	192	2	1												
14:15:00	190	0.08		2	1												
14:16:41																End of Run 4.2	
14:11:20																Start Run 5 @ FL100 called at 14:23:10	
14:24:00	45	0.08	545	2	1												
14:26:00	25	0.08		1													
14:28:00	30	0.08		2	1												
14:30:00	45	0.08		1	1												
14:32:00	40	0.07		2	1												
14:34:00	35	0.09		2													
14:36:00	30	0.08		2													
14:38:00	60	0.08	732	2	1												
14:40:00	55	0.08		2													
14:41:11																End of Run 5	
14:42:08																Start Profile 1 from FL100	
14:43:35	25	0.08	733	2												FL110	
14:44:36	10	0.09		1												FL120	
14:45:48	15	0.10		1												FL130	
14:46:48	15	0.10		1												FL140	
14:48:02	15	0.12		1												FL150	
14:49:00	10	0.08		1												FL160	
14:50:02	5	0.08		1												FL170	
14:51:06	10	0.09		10	1											FL180	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B317

Date: 15/08/07	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 09:35:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:52:01	5	0.09		10	2	2	800	500	1200							8	FL190
14:53:06	5	0.09	738	10	5	1	800	600	1200							8	FL200
14:56:30	10	0.07	950	1000	1000	2	800	180	1600							9	FL210
14:57:43	20	0.10	1090	2000	200	1	800									9	FL220
14:58:47	25	0.09	1099														FL230
14:59:49	5	0.10		1	1												FL240
15:00:55	10	0.10	1150	3000	600	1		25									End of Profile 1 @ FL250
15:03:23	5	0.10	1200	1000	200			8									Start Profile 2 from FL250
15:04:34	12	0.13	1201		Noise												FL240
15:05:40	5	0.17		1	Noise												FL230
15:06:19	5	0.10	1203	2000	1000	2	800	300	1800							9	FL220
15:07:18	6	0.08	1252	100	10	1	800	150	2000							9	FL210
15:08:10	8	0.09	1254	2000	2000	5	800	1200	1400							9	End of Profile 2 @ FL200
15:10:38																	Start Run 6 @ FL200
15:11:00	10	0.11	1382	10	10	4	800	375	1400							9	
15:13:00	15	0.08	1383	10	5			90									
15:15:00	10	0.08	1419	1000	10	1	800	130	1400							9	
15:15:24																	End of Run 6
15:23:03																	Start Run 7 @ FL150
15:24:00	10	0.07	1424	1													
15:26:00	15	0.08	1425	1													
15:28:00	10	0.09	1443														
15:28:24																	End of Run 7
15:30:47																	Start Run 8 @ FL140
15:31:00	15	0.08		1	Noise												
15:33:00	700	0.09	2215	5000	5000												
15:34:55																	End of Run 8
15:38:15																	Start Run 9 @ FL150
15:39:00	10	0.09	2316	1													
15:41:00	440	0.09	2625	4000	9000	5											
15:43:08																	End of Run 9
15:45:20																	Start Run 10 @ FL155
15:46:00	15	0.08	2923	1													
15:48:00	30	0.08	3034														
15:49:28																	End of Run 10
15:51:06																	Start Run 11 @ FL160
15:52:00	200	0.10	3124	3000	8000												
15:54:00	25	0.07	3374														
15:54:32																	End of Run 11
15:57:32																	Start Run 12 @ FL165
15:58:00	10	0.07		1													
16:00:00	10	0.07	3405														
16:02:27																	End of Run 12
16:10:57																	Start Run 13 @ 5000'
16:11:00	650	0.08	3453	5	1												
16:13:00	670	0.08		5	1												

Flight:

B317

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 20/08/2007
17:32:11**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

20/08/2007 17:12:26

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B317

Date: 15/08/2007

Instruments

1. TWC – status light flashing at 1456Z, FL200, -12C outside, Status word 4091, Para 72 TSAM out of limits (640) , TSAM reading 623 DRS units. Also, Para 75 EVAP 1 below limit (2110), reading 2087 DRSU.
2. Satcom C – Position reports being Queued but not sent. Reset CB, stopped and resubmitted messages then okay. Also, occasional messages “Satcom hardware status unavailable” at Menu option 5 – Show hardware status.
3. RVSM/ PAFT DLU – Height and Pressure reading 0ft and 1013 mb respectively at 1406Z. Reset PAFT DLU CB at 1408 then okay. This will affect derived parameters eg pressure, temps etc.
4. FFC window – froze over at high level, eventually cleared (with heater on) at 1520Z.

Note: Nevz TWC = 90 deg C, LWC = 70 deg C (for all flights from B310)

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

1 rcvd from FAAM

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B317:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Mission Scientist's log	Stephen Mobbs is typing this up.
De-brief	Stephen Mobbs is typing this up.
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 Oct 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	15 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Updated video tape holder information
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Camera

3 x Upward Facing Camera

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Prof Alan Blyth

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